

ORION | Trapezium

A Monthly Publication of the ORION Astronomical Society

The venerable Meade LX200 at TAO, opened for cleaning and refurbishment on the evening of Mon 03 Mar 2025, under Drew Bolci's expert supervision. Problems addressed included repairing a focus knob that was slipping and needed new hardware, and cleaning the corrector plate and secondary mirror. The baffle tube is visible below, set into the primary mirror. Unfortunately we could not identify the cause of the "bite" in the Airy disk noted previously in the Trapezium, see for example p.34 of the Dec 2024 issue. A follow-up Airy disk test on 12 Mar 2025 showed that this problem remains. We thank Noah Frere and his RSCC astronomy class for sharing their time, space, and facilities for this important and impromptu event.

Table of Contents

Ab initio

<i>Page Three Astronomy: 2024 YR4 / 22 Dec 2032</i>	3
<i>About ORION and TRAPEZIUM</i>	4

Messages from ORION

<i>President's Message / Astrophotography - Don Spong</i>	6
<i>TAO Director's Message - David Fields</i>	9

ORION Monthly Meeting

<i>ORION Monthly Meeting Format</i>	13
<i>Presentation 19 Mar 2025: "Planetary Imaging" by Joe Baldwin</i>	14

Events and Calendars, Sky Map and Asteroids

<i>TAO Public Stargazes in March 2025</i>	17
<i>New Stargaze Series in Oak Ridge in 2025</i>	19
<i>Second IF Stargaze in Oak Ridge: 06 Mar 2025</i>	20
<i>Star, Moon, Comet and Meteorgazing at TAO in 2025</i>	23
<i>TAO Public Stargazing: A Note Regarding Scheduling and Access in 2025</i>	24
<i>★ Public (Visitors') Calendars: Jan-Jun 2025</i>	26
<i>Staff Calendars Mar-Apr 2025</i>	28
<i>The Evening Sky Map / Mar 2025</i>	30
<i>Asteroid Flash</i>	31

Shop Talk

<i>Continuing Adventures with the Ritchey-Chrétien Astrograph - Ted Barnes</i>	33
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Appendices

<i>Astronumerology</i>	48
<i>The 80 Brightest Stars</i>	50
<i>Notable Star-Pair Angles</i>	51

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<i>Poetica</i>	53
<i>ORION and TAO General Information (and links)</i>	54
<i>Trapezium back issues online</i>	55
<i>Fin du Journal</i>	56

Page Three Astronomy

(2024 YR4) -- Earth Impact Risk Summary [\(orbit details ↗\)](#)

Torino Scale (maximum)	0
Palermo Scale (maximum)	-3.75
Palermo Scale (cumulative)	-3.60
Impact Probability (cumulative)	1.8e-5
Number of Potential Impacts	6
Impact Search Technique	IOBS

V _{impact}	17.20 km/s
V _{infinity}	13.10 km/s
H	24.0
Diameter	0.055 km
Mass	2.2e+8 kg
Energy	7.7e+0 Mt

All above are mean values weighted by impact probability

Analysis based on 442 observations spanning 65.957 days
(2024-12-25 to 2025-03-01)

Close approach to Earth 22 Dec 2032.

Impact briefly a media concern, now a very low probability.
<https://cneos.jpl.nasa.gov/sentry/details.html#?des=2024%20YR4>

The **ORION Astronomical Society** is a science and astronomy group founded in April 1974 by scientists from the United States Department of Energy facilities at Oak Ridge, Tennessee. We primarily serve the communities of Oak Ridge and Knoxville and the counties of Anderson, Knox, and Roane.

ORION's mission is to support scientific research, teaching, and astronomical activities in East Tennessee. We hold monthly public meetings at the Oak Ridge RSCC Campus, and are active at Tamke-Allan Observatory (TAO), hosting public events, sharing knowledge of the skies, and helping to provide intellectually stimulating programs. ORION works to share the wonders of the cosmos and the culture of science.

ORION members include scientists, engineers, technicians, IT experts, artists, students, and others with varied talents and expertise. Over half of ORION members own telescopes, many are amateur radio operators, and some have expertise in astrophotography.

ORION has working relationships with several organizations, including museums and other amateur astronomy groups. Membership is open to individuals who will actively contribute their time and ideas. The annual membership fee is \$20, and student discounts are available. There is no charge for our newsletters and publications, or for participation in most ORION activities.

ORION Board and Officers:

President: Don Spong

VP and Program Chair: David Fields

Social Chair: Noah Frere

Secretary: Rob Fowler

Treasurer: Bob Edwards

Editor: Ted Barnes

Astrotechnologist: Rob Scott

Videographer: Rob Fowler

Obed Site Outreach: Joshua Gray.

TRAPEZIUM is a monthly publication of the ORION Astronomical Society. The issue date is the Friday preceding the monthly ORION meeting, chosen to provide timely information regarding the planned Program.

From March 2025 we will be issuing a shorter version of the Trapezium, which will include the important information regarding the monthly ORION presentation, dates and other information regarding Public Stargazes and other notable events relating to ORION and TAO.

We expect to go through several iterations of this shorter Trapezium; we may decide that some components, such as a separate Astrophotography section, are so important for a publication on amateur astronomy that one really cannot justify excluding them.

Messages from ORION

President's Message

- Don Spong

March is an interesting time for amateur astronomers. We've got the beginning of galaxy season coming up. If anyone is motivated for a Messier Marathon, this is the month to do it. Also, we've got a lunar eclipse happening March 13. Unfortunately, the changeover to daylight savings time means many of us will tend to stay up later. April 5 – 6 is the annual Northeast Astronomy Forum in Suffern, New York; I've been to this once and highly recommend it if you have the time. This is likely when many astronomy vendors will announce new equipment, so keep an eye out for interesting new products. On a more local level, we are beginning plans for a new dome/shelter to house the large Celestron Schmidt-Cassegrain telescope that was donated by Roy Morrow.

The new moon is March 29 and full moon is March 14 (known as the Worm Moon). Regarding the planets, Jupiter, Venus (showing a nice crescent), Uranus, and Mars are in good high sky locations for visual and imaging. Saturn and Mercury are either out of view for now, or very close to the horizon. Deep Sky objects of interest include M1 (Crab nebula) in the constellation Taurus about 6500 ly, M45 (Pleiades) also in Taurus at 2200 ly, NGC 2244 (Rosette nebula) in constellation Monoceros at 5000 ly, M42 (Orion nebula) in Orion at 1600 ly, IC 434 (Horsehead and Flame nebula) in Orion at 1600 ly (see my image in the astrophoto section), IC 2118 (the Witch Head nebula) in the constellation Eridanus at 1000 ly, Sh2-308 (Dolphin nebula) in Canis Major at 4530 ly, M46 (an open cluster) in Canis Major at 5000 ly, M106 in Canis Venatici at 24 Mly, and M51 (the Whirlpool Galaxy) in Canis Venatici (off the arm of the Big Dipper) at 31 Mly.

In astrophotography, I've recently been working on objects in the constellation Orion. The following two images show the Horsehead and Flame nebulae. The image on the left was taken at TAO on February 25 with my Hyperstar attachment to get a wider field of view (focal length 390mm) and the image on the right was taken at TAO on January 28 with the 0.7 focal length reducer (focal length 1400 mm) allowing me to zoom in on the Horsehead region.

Horsehead and Flame Nebulae
(center and left)

Horsehead Nebula (detail)

The next two images were taken at TAO on the evenings February 25 and March 3. On the left is the Jellyfish nebula (IC 443) taken with my 1400 mm focal length option, and on the right is the heart nebula (Sh2-190) taken with the Hyperstar 390mm focal length. It was interesting to me that when the Jellyfish nebula is enlarged one can still see many small shock-wave structures from the original supernova, which occurred around 30,000 years ago.

Jellyfish Nebula (IC 443)

Heart Nebula (Sh2-190)

Observatory Way

The photo on the left shows our new road sign for the Roane State Tamke Allan Observatory. Traveling west, the sign is on the left as you turn into Observatory Way from Caney Creek Road, just past Joiner Hollow Road.

TAO Observatory Stargazes and Special Activities

TAO offers “dark sky” stargazes to the community on the 1st and 3rd Saturdays of each month, weather permitting. The usual schedule for the winter is to open at 7 pm and continue to nominally 10 pm, but later if the sky and attendance encourage this. After DST begins we will switch to 8 pm to 11 pm. These stargazes are supported by local astronomy clubs, especially ORION members and friends, and benefit our students and community.

Our TAO stargazes are usually well-attended, with a full classroom of visitors for evening astronomy lectures. We’ve recently missed some planned Stargazes due to inclement weather; our next planned stargazes occur on the Saturday evenings of March 15 and April 5.

Right: Noah Frere’s RSCC Astronomy class, meeting at TAO on 27 January 2025.

TAO Stargaze for International Friendship, March 2025

TAO and ORION held our second International Friendship Stargaze on Thursday evening, March 6, 2025. Telescope setup began at 6:30 pm at the International Friendship Bell just west of the Civic Center in the A.K. Bissell Park, Oak Ridge. This Bell is a historic venue for Oak Ridge and the pavilion was built with community support. We've had good participation from the RSCC Astronomy students, photo at right, and from ORION members, here showing Ted Barnes (at right) and Art Allison (below).

Art brought his Seestar S50 telescope to the 6 March event. RSCC students in the background are using an 8" Dobsonian telescope brought by David Fields. Most of the astronomers noted how difficult it was to carry telescopes, tripods, batteries *etc.* from the parking lot to the International Friendship Bell, so in the future we will set up our telescopes closer to the parking lot and will only gather at the bell for our traditional bell strike to open the event.

TAO Stargaze for International Friendship, March 2025

Dates for this event are chosen to provide a first quarter moon. As expected at our urban stargazes, the moon this March was spectacular but not blinding, and the parade of the planets offered good views of Jupiter, Venus and Mars, with dimmer views in principle of Neptune and Uranus.

Each month, we choose an honored guest to strike the bell and begin our stargaze. Our February Stargaze began with the striking of the International Friendship Bell at 7 pm by Bell supporter Pat Postma. Pat's contributions were significant in raising money for the pavilion. We discussed the importance of Astronomy and opportunities for education, and how a monthly Stargaze focused on International Friendship would benefit the community. February 3 was near the beginning of the year, and close to Valentine's Day. March 6 is very close to International Woman's Day, a day promoting international peace and tranquility.

Our March 6 International Friendship Stargaze was kicked off by a striking of the bell by Agatha Bardeel, from the Netherlands.

7:13 pm Eastern, March 6, 2025. Agatha Bardeel releases the Kraken.

ORION Monthly Meeting
3rd Wednesday

ORION Monthly Meeting Format

Meeting Venue: City Room (A-111), just inside the main entrance, Coffey/McNalley Bldg., Oak Ridge Campus, Roane State Community College. 7:00 pm Eastern, 3rd Wednesday of each month.

Our monthly meetings (except for December, a dinner) generally proceed as follows:

- Welcome
- Announcements
- Invited Presentation and Discussion
- Awarding of the Mug
- Astrophotography / Special Presentations

The nominal start time is 7:00 pm Eastern, on the 3rd Wednesday of the month. The beginning of the meeting will usually include announcements of general interest.

Meetings typically continue until around 9:00 pm. Please plan to stay until the end. Hopefully we will all enjoy the astrophotography and other special topics discussed in the latter part of the meeting.

Remote Viewing: A live Zoom session will usually be open during the ORION Monthly Meeting, at the link:

<https://us02web.zoom.us/j/88528735960?pwd=KzY4bnBHcjlhTzg3L3pOcjY0TFovUT09> or
<https://bit.ly/42apGxX>

Meeting ID: 885 2873 5960 Passcode: 716689

Title: Planetary Imaging

Speaker: Joe Baldwin

Abstract:

A step-by-step tutorial on capturing and processing live video. Additional discussions / tips for successful data collection and camera / optics selection.

Mini Bio:

I am a Senior Electrical Engineer at Oak Ridge National Laboratory, working in the autonomous systems group developing flight control, communications, and measurement systems. My fascination with astronomy began in my youth, observing nature's wonders alongside my father. From chasing comet Halley to southern Florida in 1986 to annual expeditions to secluded dark-site areas for meteor showers, my journey has been woven with a deep connection to the cosmos.

My astronomical hobby has been supported by a diverse collection of telescopes, ranging from the venerable Celestron C8 on an AC equatorial mount to larger dobbs, refractors, and versatile Schmidt-Cassegrains. Over the years, I have primarily focused on planetary and solar imaging, leveraging cutting-edge advancements in cameras, optics, and software to capture the intricate details of our celestial neighbors with modest equipment.

ORION Monthly Meeting (as planned):

19 Feb 2025

Our Monthly ORION speaker on Wed 19 Feb 2025 was to have been Joe Baldwin, on the topic of Planetary Imaging. According to his Abstract, this would be “*A step-by-step tutorial on capturing and processing live video. Additional discussions / tips for successful data collection and camera / optics selection.*” Something of considerable interest to ORION of course.

Alas the already legendary Winter of 2025 was not yet through with us, and when the date arrived we found that we were in for snow and deep cold by East Tennessee standards. Those of us who lived in the more rural settings appeared unlikely to go anywhere, and when RSCC closed their Oak Ridge facilities, the planned 19 Feb ORION Monthly meeting was deferred. The obvious next step if possible was to hold the meeting on the 4th Wednesday, 26 Feb 2025, if that was ok with the Weather Gods. In the event this date too proved problematic, so the Monthly Meeting was postponed until Wed 19 Mar 2025.

This of course wasn't all bad; a snow day or two was a good opportunity to continue working on the Mar 2025 Trapezium.

The morning of 19 Feb 2025, a cold and snowy third Wednesday in East Tennessee.

Events and Calendars, Sky Map and Asteroids

TAO Public Stargazes in March:

Sat 01 & 15 Mar 2025

Sat 01 Mar 2025

Sunset	6:35 pm
Civ dusk	7:01 pm
Ast dusk	8:00 pm
Moonrise	8:03 am
Moonset	8:47 pm
Moon illum.	04%

Sat 15 Mar 2025

Sunset	6:47 pm
Civ dusk	7:13 pm
Ast dusk	8:13 pm
Moonrise	8:17 pm
Moonset*	7:45 am
	*16 May
Moon illum.	98%

TAO Public Stargazes in March: (cont.) Sat 01 Mar 2025

On this date we had expected to welcome a large number of home schooled visitors, likely as the first of two sessions. Unfortunately the weather didn't cooperate, the sky was predicted to be mostly overcast, so this event was cancelled. This was the 5th planned Public Stargaze at TAO, and four were cancelled due to inclement weather. We hope for improved weather on the next scheduled TAO Public Stargaze, on 15 Mar 2025.

New Stargaze Series in Oak Ridge in 2025

A new series of monthly Stargaze events was initiated in Oak Ridge on Monday 03 Feb 2025, with the second on Thu 06 Mar 2025. ORION plans to continue these monthly International Friendship Stargaze (IFS) events near the Peace Bell in A. K. Bissell Park.

This event is intended to bring enjoyment of the evening skies to people in the Oak Ridge, Clinton and surrounding areas who may find the 30-mile trip to TAO for one of our existing bimonthly 1st and 3rd Sat Public Stargaze events too onerous. Although the background light levels are rather high in the Oak Ridge area, it is still possible to view interesting objects such as the moon, planets and stars through our telescopes.

Dates for future IFS Stargazes will be announced in the Trapezium, and on the ORIONastronomy at groups.io.

30-mileer predictions for this date prove to be unfavorable, a change of plans will be announced on ORION astronomy at groups.io. It may be useful to follow the Oak Ridge area astronomy weather predictions on Clear Sky Charts (cleardarksky dot com) and Astrospheric (astropheric dot com), to see whether the weather (smile emoji) for the planned date appears favorable in advance.

Visitors are encouraged to interact with ORION astronomers who have set up and may be operating telescopes and other astronomical equipment. We enjoy public discussions, and regard this sharing of

information as a primary goal of our organization.

Please confirm the time and date of the event in advance before proceeding to the site, as these may have been changed.

Parking is available nearby, near the Oak Ridge Social Center building in the park; it's a short walk from there to the Peace Bell area. Since this is not a dark-sky location, no special lighting preparations are required, although those who have astronomy headlights may wish to bring them. Similarly, people who wish to bring their own outdoor seating, binoculars, telescopes and so forth are welcome to participate.

During DST (Apr-Oct IFS events), public telescope viewing will be from 8:00 pm until 9:00 pm, longer if there is public interest. Setup time for ORION astronomers will be half an hour before viewing. Outside of DST, all these times will be an hour earlier. The early times of this event are chosen with school age kiddies in mind.

1st IFS Stargaze, Mon 03 Feb 2025.

The second monthly International Friendship Stargaze was held in Oak Ridge on Thu 06 Mar 2025, near the Peace Bell in A. K. Bissell Park. The first of this series had attracted a significant number of ORION associated amateur astronomers, as well as several “accidental” passersby. The hours were unchanged; equipment setup starting at 6:30 pm, the event starting at 7:00 pm, and a nominal shutdown at 8:00 pm. (We actually departed about 8:30 pm.)

This event was less well attended, perhaps because of a sudden return to cold weather. Attending astronomers with equipment were Art Allison with his Seestar, Ted Barnes with a remote telescope setup, David Fields with a Dobsonian, and Noah Frere with his class of about 10 RSCC astronomy students. Ted was accompanied by his spouse Agatha Bardoel as our international gong ringer (to start the event), and David brought a guest, Sue Dyson, at least for the initial part. Larry Davidson and D.R. Fudge both appeared, but Larry declined to set up his telescope since we had few visitors, and the walk from the car park to the Peace Bell area is excessive with significant equipment.

Ted found that a small green utility structure just West of the seating area provided AC power (2 sockets), and David provided a long weatherproof extension cord, so this month we had AC power.

Although we had about 10 students from Noah’s class, we had very few visitors on this cold night. Additional publicity for the event is evidently needed, perhaps through notices in the library and the Oak Ridger.

This 2nd IFStargaze encountered several gremlins. Agatha rang the gong so enthusiastically that the recoil knocked her to the ground, and she sprained her wrist.

Although Ted had successfully tested his AnyDesk link to his Ritchey-Chrétien Astrograph before departing, when he tried to complete the wireless

Second IFStargaze in Oak Ridge: (cont.) Thu 06 Mar 2025

connection from Oak Ridge, AnyDesk reported that this remote computer was not available. A test AnyDesk link to Rob Fowler (who was safe and warm at home in Oak Ridge) went through successfully, so it appeared that the problem with the connection to Ted's remote telescope was at his home observatory in Clinton. On returning it was discovered that a WiFi repeater needed to get a strong signal to his remote telescope cpu had accidentally been unplugged just before departure. So at least *that* gremlin was identified and hopefully eliminated.

Since the remote telescope facility (RTF) demonstration wasn't working, Ted could only show his system and connection procedures to the RSCC students without any actual live remote telescope images present. Maybe next month.

So, for April we can hope for warmer weather, clear skies, and more attendees. We may change our setup site to a small grassy area close to parking that we used for the 1st meeting, which requires relatively little walking; only the opening gong needs to be at the Peace Bell itself.

Agatha Bardoel preparing to release the mighty gong.

A Remote Telescope demonstration with no remote telescope. (When working it looks rather like the background image of Procyon at right.) Here we at least have an AnyDesk chat window open to Rob Fowler, and a nice remote view of Rob's Desktop on the right half of the large screen.

Star, Moon, Comet and Meteorgazing at TAO in 2025

We enthusiastically invite visitors to attend our Public Stargaze events, held at our dark-sky site, the Tamke-Allan Observatory (TAO) near Kingston, Tennessee. These events are intended especially for visitors, so our buildings and facilities will be open, and there will be astronomy talks as well as public skywatching.

In Jan-Jun 2025 we plan to hold fixed-calendar public Stargaze events on the 1st and 3rd Saturday of each month. These weekend events are especially appropriate for families. We also hold public special events, such as a “Full Moonrise,” with associated Moon Music, and the occasional comet watch. The annual Perseid Meteor watch in mid-August is especially popular.

The precise dates of many of these events depend on the local weather conditions, and cannot be specified *definitively* long in advance. As an approximate guide, see the TAOCalendar pages following. Once a date is finalized we usually confirm it through the ORION online message site ORION astronomy@groups.io. Likely and unlikely dates for TAO events may be inferred from the weather predictions at TAO by Clear Sky Charts (cleardarksky dot com) and Astrospheric (astrospheric dot com).

Please confirm event dates before proceeding to TAO.

In view of the rather challenging approach road to TAO, “Observatory Way,” first-time visitors should plan to arrive before dark. Driving instructions are given at: <https://www.roanestate.edu/pages/obs/visit.htm>

Some instructions follow, since people may be unfamiliar with procedures for stargazing at a dark-sky site.

ORION members are invited to arrive early with their telescopes and mounts, to prepare for evening observing and to share refreshments. Please bring a red flashlight, or a headband with a red-light option.

Visitors who wish to acquire red lights or red-light headbands for observing may find them at many commercial amateur astronomy sites, such as [https:// www dot high pointscientific dot com](https://www.highpointscientific.com). The “Lepro LE” LED Headlamp, **model 3200008**, available from Amazon for about \$10 (Aug. 2024) is a personal favorite. This is rechargeable and has separate red and white led buttons, with several brightness settings. A caution: For amateur astronomy, brighter lights are NOT preferred, and WHITE lights are highly discouraged. Please use only red lights while the Stargaze is in progress.

Parking is available on site; on entering TAO **stay to the right**, and *please use the parking area below and right (Southwest) of the TAO buildings and observing area, near the treeline*. And **PLEASE NO HEADLIGHTS ON SITE.**

Visitors are encouraged to interact with ORION astronomers who have set up and may be operating telescopes and other astronomical equipment. We enjoy public discussions, and regard this sharing of information as a primary goal of our organization. Visitors are welcome to coffee and other refreshments.

TAO Public Stargazing: A Note Regarding Scheduling and Access in 2025

In 2025 we will revert to an earlier schedule of having our Public Stargaze nights on every first and third Saturday. Of course this assumes good weather; if the weather is not suitable, a changed schedule will be announced on the group site [ORIONastronomy @ groups.io](https://groups.io/OrionAstronomy).

We decided that the previous (2024) schedule of a once-monthly Public Stargaze was insufficient, and having a moon visible in some phase other than close to New gives our visitors an obvious and interesting object for viewing.

Since winter sunsets are rather early, our nominal visitor hours for Public Stargazes during the first two months of 2025 will be 7:00 pm - 10:00 pm. The planned Public Stargaze dates in Jan and Feb of 2025 are 4 Jan, 18 Jan, 1 Feb and 15 Feb. From mid-March 2025, with Daylight Savings Time we plan to revert to 8:00 pm - 11:00 pm.

In general, if it is already dark please dim your headlights on arrival at the TAO grounds, follow the right branch of the access road, and park to the right of the TAO building, near the treeline.

Note: Parking in or near the elevated flat observing area at the front (East) of the TAO building is reserved for astronomers who are bringing their equipment.

Additional information for visitors may be found on the previous and following two pages of this issue.

Public (Visitors') Calendar

Jan-Jun 2025 (1 pp.)

The principle public events for visitors are the Public Stargazes, held during Jan-Jun 2025 on the 1st and 3rd Saturday of each month. Public Stargazes may be added to the calendar on other dates as we progress through the year. If so, notices and revised Calendars will appear in the Trapezium and online. Other to be announced public events of special interest to visitors include the occasional Full Moonrise and Meteor showers, Lunar eclipses and Comet watches. The facilities in the TAO buildings onsite will be open to the public during these events. We recommend checking a TAO website such as ORIONAstronomy @ groups.io before visiting, to confirm that listed events will proceed as planned; weather conditions may require a cancellation or change of date.

TAO Calendar Jan-Jun 2025 (public fixed calendar events)

date	event	details	start	end
Sat 04 Jan 2025	★	1 st Sat Stargaze	7:00 pm	10:00 pm
Sat 18 Jan 2025	★	3 rd Sat Stargaze	7:00 pm	10:00 pm
Sat 01 Feb 2025	★	1 st Sat Stargaze	7:00 pm	10:00 pm
Sat 15 Feb 2025	★	3 rd Sat Stargaze	7:00 pm	10:00 pm
Sat 01 Mar 2025	★	1 st Sat Stargaze	7:00 pm	10:00 pm
Sat 15 Mar 2025	★	3 rd Sat Stargaze	8:00 pm	11:00 pm
Sat 05 Apr 2025	★	1 st Sat Stargaze	8:00 pm	11:00 pm
Sat 19 Apr 2025	★	3 rd Sat Stargaze	8:00 pm	11:00 pm
Sat 03 May 2025	★	1 st Sat Stargaze	9:00 pm	midnight
Sat 17 May 2025	★	3 rd Sat Stargaze	9:00 pm	midnight
Sat 07 Jun 2025	★	1 st Sat Stargaze	9:00 pm	midnight
Sat 21 Jun 2025	★	3 rd Sat Stargaze	9:00 pm	midnight

These first-half of 2025 TAO Public Events will be held at TAO on fixed calendar days during the weekend, which will hopefully prove convenient for many visitors.

Staff Calendars

Mar-Apr 2025

The events listed in the staff calendars (which include public stargazes) are primarily intended for ORION members or other experienced astronomers. Any Dark Stargazes listed here are intended especially for Astrophotography. Other special events for experienced astronomers who require the dark skies listed in these calendars may include Asteroid Occultations and other research projects, which may not be scheduled long in advance. Members of the public who wish to participate in these special staff events may wish to contact TAO staff or ORION Board members and make arrangements prior to the event.

The 2025 Staff Calendars are still in development, and will appear here in more complete form as events are added.

TAO Calendar Mar 2024

(public and staff /special events)

date	event	details	start	end
Sat 01 Mar 2025	★	1 st Sat Public Stargaze	7:00 pm	10:00 pm
Thu 06 Mar 2025	★	International Friendship Stargaze (Oak Ridge)	7:00 pm (6:30 pm setup)	8:00 pm
Fri 14 Mar 2025	○	Full Moon 02:55 am Eastern		
”	●	Total Lunar Eclipse	2:26 am (tot.)	3:32 am (tot.)
Sat 15 Mar 2025	★	3 rd Sat Public Stargaze	8:00 pm	11:00 pm
Sat 22 Mar 2025	★	Occultation (11 secs) 14 Irene 11:00:33 pm Eastern	5:30 pm	midnight
Sat 29 Mar 2025	●	New Moon 06:58 am Eastern		

DST in 2025 begins on Sunday 9 Mar 2025; 2:00 am transitions to 3:00 am. Eastern Daylight Time is 4 hrs behind UT.

TAO Calendar Apr 2024

(public and staff /special events)

date	event	details	start	end
Thu 03 Apr 2025		International Friendship Stargaze (Oak Ridge)	8:00 pm (7:00 pm setup)	9:00 pm
Sat 05 Apr 2025		1 st Sat Public Stargaze	8:00 pm	11:00 pm
Sat 12 Apr 2025		Full Moon 08:22 pm Eastern		
Mon 14 Apr 2025		Occultation (repeat) 785 Zwetana 01:46:20 am Eastern	5:30 pm	3:00 am
Sat 19 Apr 2025		3 rd Sat Public Stargaze	8:00 pm	11:00 pm
Sun 27 Apr 2025		New Moon 03:31 pm Eastern		

Asteroid Flash ...

Next “bright star” (mag < 10.0) asteroid occultation at TAO:

Sat 22 Mar 2025, 11:00:33 pm Eastern

Magnitude **9.5** star **TYC 1892-00151-1**
will be occulted by magnitude 11.0 asteroid
14 Irene
(a biggie!)

Max duration **11.2 seconds**

In Gemini, Alt@Azi = 56° @ 271°

No Moon will be available for this event.

Shop Talk

Continuing Adventures with the Ritchey-Chrétien Astrograph:

- Ted Barnes

Last month I contributed a “shop talk” kind of article titled “*Adventures with the Ritchey-Chrétien Astrograph*,” in which I discussed my attempts to learn about and use the somewhat exotic 8” ORION Ritchey-Chrétien reflector I had purchased “nearly new” through Noah Frere at an ORION meeting in Nov 2024. Since this telescope has two hyperbolic mirrors, and purportedly might be difficult to focus and / or collimate, I thought I could be in for an adventure.

The 8” ORION Ritchey-Chrétien Astrograph initially spent two months sitting on my workbench at my home observatory, LRO. Eventually by mid-Jan 2025, as very cold temperatures were keeping everyone from visiting TAO, I decided to start working on using this somewhat exotic piece of equipment. This is my second installment in this series.

Actually I encountered few difficulties, and they were minor ones, such as how best to use the double mounting rails on the OTA (it has both Losmandy and Vixen style rails, on opposite sides of the OTA). The assumingly intended setup of Losmandy on the bottom (here, mounted on my CGX mount), and Vixen on top, has worked rather well. I removed a Telrad finder, and converted the 60 mm Orion finder scope to a guide scope with a ZWO ASI290MMmini camera attached, running PHD2 guiding.

Adding a laser

I also added a laser finder, but had to attach it to the Losmandy mount beneath the OTA, since the predrilled mounting holes in the OTA didn't fit the holes in the laser bracket “shoe.” (The OTA hole pair is 25 mm apart, whereas the “shoe” hole pair is 20 mm apart. Sigh.) There are several advantages in mounting the laser finder beneath the OTA. First, one has easier hand access to the laser; second, the laser beam no longer hits the lower edge of the observatory roof long before the OTA optical axis does; and third, the laser charging cord has a much shorter run.

Continuing Adventures with the Ritchey-Chrétien Astrograph:

(cont.)

To add a shop comment of an extreme “nuts and bolts” character, I found that one can protect the front lens end of the usual Chinese green laser pointer (fm. Amazon) from the elements using a Chinese 3/4” (19 mm) I.D. soft black rubber cap (also fm. Amazon, mfg. by Uxcell, about \$9 for a lot of 25), just what one needs; see below.

Laser pointer with soft black rubber cap (cap at left).

Detail showing how the laser power button can be held in the “on” position using a toothed plastic spring clamp (white front toothed jaws at left, black end paddles at right). The clamp surrounds a piece of paper towel wrapped around the laser, and holds down the “on” button. The paper towel provides sufficient friction to stop the clamp from slipping off the laser body.

Continuing Adventures with the Ritchey-Chrétien Astrograph:

(cont.)

I learn how to use a lens cap

Another point about using the Ritchey-Chrétien which I discovered only recently involves the OTA's lens cap (see the image on the first page of this story). Initially the lens cap seemed to be only weakly held in place, and when transporting the OTA horizontally in my van the lens cap often fell off. I thought perhaps some shims were missing. It was only recently that I discovered that once you had put the lens cap on the OTA, you could rotate it clockwise (facing it), and it would slide into a secure holding position. Remarkable. I never knew! I wonder if I have missed a similar feature in the other reflectors I have owned.

As I noted in a second article last month, "*The Calamitous TAO Occultation of 29 Jan 2025*," by the end of January this telescope was working rather well, and I was able to use it successfully in capturing an asteroid occultation, using small images and rather fast 20 ms frames. My own "calamity" was the gps coax connecting my QHY174M GPS camera to its antenna lost electrical contact, so I lost my gps timing data; the Ritchey-Chrétien itself performed quite well.

Optical tests

OK, lets proceed with some recent optical tests. One of my favorite procedures is to capture a full-frame image of a star field, and then use the All Sky Plate Solver (ASPS) to identify the star field, and read off various camera and telescope parameters from the output of this program. As input ASPS needs the detector (camera) pixel size, and a first approximation to the system's focal length. As output you learn the actual (fitted) focal length, the coordinates of the image center, the image field in pixels and in arcmins, and the camera (image) orientation angle relative to North.

On 17 Feb 2025 at my home observatory "LRO" I captured several images of Procyon, Acubens (α Cnc), and Regulus, a mix of single images and stacks. For all of these images I used my QHY174M GPS camera (with 5.86 μ m pixels) with the gps enabled, in MONO8 mode, with full field being 1920x1200 pixels.

Here I will first discuss ASPS results from a stack of 66 raw frames (no post processing) of Acubens. Each frame was 4 secs at a gain of 400, so the stack is 66x4sG400 in my notation. The sensor temperature was -31C, and I usually used PHD2 guiding while capturing the stacks. The recorded time at completion of the 66 frames was 7:48:56 pm Eastern; the raw image is shown on the following page.

Continuing Adventures with the Ritchey-Chrétien Astrograph:

(cont.)

A raw MONO8 full-field (1920x1200 px) image of Acubens and field, a stack of 66x4sG400 frames (hence total exposure 264 secs) taken with a QHY174MGPS camera attached to the Ritchey-Chrétien. Completed 7:48:56 pm Eastern, 17 Feb 2025, at LRO.

Results from the ASPS regarding this image.

Continuing Adventures with the Ritchey-Chrétien Astrograph:

(cont.)

ASPS finds that the image center is at RA 08 58 28 and Dec +11 51 26 in J2000 coordinates. Of course this is not exactly the location of Acubens, which according to Gaia (rounded) is at RA 08 58 29.20 and Dec +11 51 27.6; our Alignment set is good but not perfect, and anyway ASPS doesn't display fractions of RA or Dec seconds. The fitted focal length is 1616 mm, whereas the Ritchey-Chrétien officially has a focal length of 1600 mm.

Regarding magnitude limits, most of the faint stars easily visible in the previous image are on the bright side (16.5-17.0) of 17th magnitude (16.5-17.5), although a few faint smudges can be seen that Gaia lists as 18th or even 19th g-magnitude stars. For example, the Gaia star **EDR3 604791421740052864** at 08 58 45.54, +11 56 38.4, listed as g-mag 18.504(3), is visible as a very faint smudge in this raw image. This 18th / 19th g-magnitude star must be near the faintness limit for this raw stack.

To concentrate on a few specific faintish stars, I identified several in the Gaia database that were clearly evident as more or less faint smudges in the raw image, using the Aladin v12.0 online viewer to access the Gaia database. The stars selected (listed by magnitude) and their (rounded) J2000 Gaia [or other] coordinates are

star	g-mag [mag]	RA	Dec
a	16.10	08 58 45.88	11 54 14.3
b	16.61	08 58 42.46	11 55 50.3
c	16.98	08 58 44.24	11 52 59.0
[d]	[16.99]	[08 58 46.2	11 55 22]
[e]	[17.58]	[08 58 58.0	11 54 47]
f	17.67	08 58 49.67	11 55 32.0
g	18.09	08 59 00.66	11 55 24.8
h	18.504	08 58 45.54	11 56 38.4

Assuming that our identification of these stars is correct (and the latter few are probably correct, but are certainly indistinct), we have found that stars can be identified in this 66x4sG400 raw image stack down to 19th magnitude.

Continuing Adventures with the Ritchey-Chrétien Astrograph:

(cont.)

The “stars” [d] and [e] in the table above, with their information in square brackets, are actually asteroids. They are respectively 6509 Giovanniprateresi and 44390 1998 ST63, and these are the coordinates and visual magnitudes assigned by TheSkyX and JPL Horizons for 7:45 pm Eastern, 17 Feb 2025. I first noticed the brighter one as a *ca.* 16.5 mag “star” that was missing from the Aladin DSS2 deep sky chart. On loading the available asteroid data (for over 1.4M asteroids) into TheSkyX, a search for asteroids in this field at this time found just these two in the magnitude range 15.0-19.0, and 6509 Giovanniprateresi was a perfect fit for this “extra” star. These asteroid positions and magnitudes are sufficiently accurate to use these two asteroids as additional sources.

Next we test whether post processing our raw image of Acubens and field changes any of the results we obtain by plate solving the raw image using ASPS. We used fairly conventional techniques with the Windows Live Photo Gallery to increase the contrast in the raw image, darken the background, and sharpen the star images. Our resulting post-processed image is shown below; for comparison the raw image is two pages back.

Continuing Adventures with the Ritchey-Chrétien Astrograph:

(cont.)

On running ASPS on the post-processed image on the previous page, we find an identical set of “Astronomy results” to those shown three pages previously (except of course that the name of the file on the top line differs). This is reassuring of course, but need not have been the case. One can try using different inputs, such as an initially assumed focal length of 1630 mm instead of 1600 mm, and confirm that the same final fit numbers result. One must be careful to use the ASPS pulldown tab “Edit → Clear astrometry results” to reset a run, and “Settings → Plate solver settings ...” to change the starting values.

Camera orientation

As a final comment on the ASPS output parameters, note that the fitted Camera angle reported by ASPS, 179.84° , seems surprisingly close to perfectly aligned with celestial North. This is of course not an accident; I discovered that on SharpCap v. 4.1 one may use the pulldown routine “Tools → Plate Solve (Solve only),” and if a live image with sufficient stars is present, SharpCap will solve for the field and print helpful related information to the screen. In addition to the RA and Dec of the field center, this routine also gives orientation information about how many degrees and tenths the image “up” direction differs from North.

This is extremely useful, as one can iteratively adjust the camera orientation, and read out the new orientation relative to North from the live image, which is a fairly simple and rapid procedure. After a few iterations one can easily orient the camera to within *ca.* 0.2° of North.

Comparing ASPS results for star positions from raw vs. post-processed images

Next we compare our ASPS-determined positions for the eight faint “stellar” sources listed in the table two pages above, from

- 1) the “raw” (softer and smoother and greyer) image,
- 2) the post-processed (sharper, more black and white) image.

Continuing Adventures with the Ritchey-Chrétien Astrograph:

(cont.)

In this table, following each set of (rounded) Gaia RA and Dec values for each star position, we show the ASPS-determined positions determined from the digitized, contrast-enhanced ASPS images. The first line gives the “raw” image position, followed by the positions from post-processed image.

star	g-mag [mag]	RA	Dec
a	16.10	08 58 45.88	11 54 14.3
raw image		08 58 45	11 54 13
p-p image		08 58 45	11 54 13
b	16.61	08 58 42.46	11 55 50.3
		08 58 42	11 55 48
		08 58 42	11 55 49
c	16.98	08 58 44.24	11 52 59.0
		08 58 44	11 52 58
		08 58 44	11 52 59
[d]	[16.99]	[08 58 46.2	11 55 22]
		08 58 46	11 55 21
		08 58 46	11 55 21
[e]	[17.58]	[08 58 58.0	11 54 47]
		08 58 57	11 54 46
f	17.67	08 58 49.67	11 55 32.0
		08 58 49	11 55 33
g	18.09	08 59 00.66	11 55 24.8
		08 59 00	11 55 25
h	18.504	08 58 45.54	11 56 38.4
		08 58 45	11 56 37

Continuing Adventures with the Ritchey-Chrétien Astrograph:

(cont.)

Note that these two sets of positions from “raw” and “post-processed” images are essentially identical, if both are present. So, for position determinations of faint stars, it doesn’t matter whether we run ASPS on the “raw” or “post-processed” image.

An important difference in “raw” versus “post-processed” images

What does show a difference is the limiting magnitude of the “raw” versus “post-processed” image. We conclude that one should use “raw” images in ASPS. This is probably our most important observation:

The four fainter stars visible in the “raw” image did not survive in the “post-processed” image; these soft, weak enhancements were simply mapped into dark pixels, with a few scattered white ones that did not form an image. So, **in replacing a raw image by a post-processed one, about a magnitude of sensitivity to faint stars is lost**, at least in this example.

Regarding a possible systematic error in ASPS coordinates

There is some evidence, especially in RA, that in reducing the resolution of displayed results to integer seconds, the actual ASPS result for RA seconds was simply truncated. In the cases for which we have both raw and p-p results, the ASPS RA seconds are identical, and the difference of the RA seconds (Gaia minus ASPS) over the full set of eight sources averages to 0.58, close to the discrepancy of 0.5 one would expect from simple truncation. It would be helpful to get another two digits of RA accuracy from this program, and one more digit in Dec. (RA and Dec units of course usually differ in length by about an order of magnitude.) Unfortunately it’s not clear if anyone is maintaining ASPS at present.

I did also capture a single frame image of Procyon. That (raw) image, a single frame of 4sG300 taken at 7:27 pm Eastern, 17 Feb 2025, is shown on the following page. The ASPS output gives slightly different values for the focal length 1617 mm, pixel scale 0.747”, and

Continuing Adventures with the Ritchey-Chrétien Astrograph:

(cont.)

Procyon

I also captured a single-frame image of Procyon at LRO. That (raw) 4sG300 image, taken at 7:27 pm Eastern 17 Feb 2025, is shown below. ASPS gives slightly different values for the focal length (1617 mm), pixel scale (0.747"), and camera angle (179.80°). The reported f.o.v. is unchanged at 23'x14'. (The previous ASPS raw-image stack numbers are shown on the ASPS output screen six pages earlier.) The image center coordinates here are RA 07 39 16 and Dec +05 12 37. Rounded Simbad J2000 coordinates for Procyon are the nearby RA 07 39 18.12 and Dec = +05 13 30.0. Unfortunately the corresponding DSS2 image in Aladin is difficult to use in extracting faint stars for comparison, as it is very bright in the region near Procyon. One faint star near the sensitivity limit (from bottom right) is shown on the following page.

25 02 18 00:27:14:7115444 Z

A raw MONO8 full-field (1920x1200 px) image of Procyon and field, a single 4sG300 frame captured at LRO on 17 Feb 2025, gps timestamped 2025 02 18 00:27:14:7115444 Z. (Z is for Zulu, implying UT.)

Continuing Adventures with the Ritchey-Chrétien Astrograph:

(cont.)

Here we show a 16th magnitude star near the faint magnitude limit of the image on the previous page. The positions of the ASPS exposure slider settings are shown in the ASPS panel detail at right.

A star near the faint magnitude limit of this single-exposure, moderate gain 4sG300 field. Rounded J2000 Gaia coordinates are RA 07 38 31.57, Dec +05 08 28.1, g-magnitude 15.74 . This 16th magnitude star is officially **Gaia EDR3 3138156548186909568**.

ASPS “slider” enhancement settings used in identifying the faint star at left. Note the red and green markers, which have selected a slight reduction in the brightness of the brightest pixels, and a great increase in the fainter ones. This greatly stretches the contrast around the pixel distribution (white peak).

Continuing Adventures with the Ritchey-Chrétien Astrograph:

(cont.)

Testing a Barlow on the Ritchey-Chrétien

Probably most serious amateur astronomers own Barlow lenses, but these may not get much use. Although changing the field of view by simply inserting an element sounds attractive, this often seems to encounter difficulties, due to insufficient travel available to allow focus, or simply due to the awkwardness of dealing with the combined optical system. As I have a Meade 2x telenegative “shorty” Barlow available, I thought it would be interesting to see if this could be added to the Ritchey-Chrétien / QHY174MGPS system described here, and whether the combined system performed as expected.

Since the RC and camera both had 2” apertures, but the Barlow was a 1¼” cylinder on both ends, putting the Barlow in the middle required searching for appropriate adapters. This was eventually successful, and the combined RC – Barlow – QHY174 system is shown below.

Without the Barlow, focus had required a focuser setting of close to 0.9 cm on the upper scale. Since I had no idea how this combined system would perform, I decided that I needed a bright light source, and chose Regulus. After removing the OTA lens cap I was greeted by a large bright friendly Airy disk in SharpCap, which I was able to bring to focus thanks to a generous focuser barrel. As you can see, obtaining focus required pulling out the barrel by an additional 3 cm. The resulting image of Regulus, in a single unprocessed MONO8 4 sec exposure at a gain of 400 (4sG400), is shown on the following page.

Continuing Adventures with the Ritchey-Chrétien Astrograph:

(cont.)

Single frame 4sG400 image of Regulus using the RC – Barlow – QHY174 combined system. Imaged at LRO, 9:16 pm Eastern 17 Feb 2025.

A simulated aperture of 10.8' x 6.75' using TheSkyX, for comparison with the actual image at left. Only approximate, not a fit.

Continuing Adventures with the Ritchey-Chrétien Astrograph:

(cont.)

The image of Regulus obtained with the Barlow is at left, and at right is an “eyeballed” approximation to this field using TheSkyX. The f.o.v. shown at right is 10.8' x 6.75'; since the full field without the Barlow is 23.8' x 14.9', the Barlow has reduced it by a linear scale of about 2.2. It would be nice for someone to do some remedial reading in optics (*e.g.* Born and Wolf) to understand and explain this number.

Since only four stars are evident in this field, there was no point in trying to understand the image using ASPS. Perhaps an image of a compact open cluster would be useful as a follow-on test case.

I also attempted to image a more diffuse object using this RC - Barlow - QHY174 system, a relatively bright barred spiral galaxy (M95 in Leo). I captured a 60s single exposure at a gain of 480; stacking shorter frames was unsuccessful, since too few alignment stars were visible in this small field. The 60sG480 frame was also unsuccessful; one could tell that this was a barred spiral, but the image was foggy and low contrast, and little detail was evident. This system shows more promise without the Barlow.

Appendices

Astronomy

- tb

Some numbers are quoted to several-digit accuracy where appropriate.
Exact numerical relationships are indicated as such.

1 ly = 1 ly (Julian) = *exactly* 9 460 730 472 580. 8 km = 63 241. 077 084 ... AU
c = speed of light = *exactly* 299 792 458 m/s = *exactly* ☺ 1 ly/yr.
1 AU = *exactly* 149 597 870. 7 km
1 parsec (pc) = 3. 261 598 ... light years (ly)
1 yr (Julian) = *exactly* 365.25 d = *exactly* 31 557 600 s
1 d = *exactly* 86 400 s

distance to α Cen A = 1.346(2) pc = 4.390(8) ly
distance to the center of the galaxy ~ 8 kpc ~ 25 kly (considerable uncertainty)

1 nm = 1 nanometer = 10^{-9} m *exactly*
 H_{α} wavelength = 656.2 nm

+ 0.5 change in magnitude	= <i>exactly</i> $10^{1/5}$ x fainter =	1. 584 893 ... x fainter
+ 1 change in magnitude	= <i>exactly</i> $10^{2/5}$ x fainter =	2. 511 886 ... x fainter
+ 2 change in magnitude	= <i>exactly</i> $10^{4/5}$ x fainter =	6. 309 ... x fainter
+ 2.5 change in mag	= <i>exactly</i> 10^1 x fainter =	10 x fainter
+ 3 change in mag	= <i>exactly</i> $10^{6/5}$ x fainter =	15. 848 ... x fainter
+ 4 change in mag	= <i>exactly</i> $10^{8/5}$ x fainter =	39. 810 ... x fainter
+ 5 change in mag	= <i>exactly</i> 10^2 x fainter =	100 x fainter
+ 6 change in mag	= <i>exactly</i> $10^{12/5}$ x fainter =	251. 188 ... x fainter
+ 7.5 change in mag	= <i>exactly</i> 10^3 x fainter =	1000 x fainter
+ 8 change in mag	= <i>exactly</i> $10^{16/5}$ x fainter =	1584. 893 ... x fainter
+ 10 change in mag	= <i>exactly</i> 10^4 x fainter =	10 000 x fainter
+ 20 change in mag	= <i>exactly</i> 10^8 x fainter =	100 000 000 x fainter

Brightness is proportional to $1 / \text{distance}^2$

10 x more distant = *exactly* 10^2 x fainter = + 5 change in magnitude
 10^2 x more distant = *exactly* 10^4 x fainter = + 10 change in mag
 10^3 x more distant = *exactly* 10^6 x fainter = + 15 change in mag

Absolute magnitude M_{abs} is the brightness as seen from a distance of 10 pc
 M_{abs} (our sun) = 4.83

17th mag is about 1 optical photon / cm^2 s (Barnes's rule ☺)

Astronomy (cont.)

Some numbers are quoted to several-digit accuracy where appropriate. *Exact* numerical relationships are indicated as such.

R.A. = RA = Right Ascension = the angle ϕ around the celestial polar axis, usually quoted in hours, minutes, and seconds (*h m s*); analogous to longitude.

Dec = Declination = the angle θ above the celestial equator, usually quoted in degrees, minutes, and seconds ($^{\circ} \ ' \ ''$); analogous to latitude.

The RA (ϕ) and Dec (θ) angles, together with a reference epoch such as J2000.0, specify an object's direction in the sky.

A unit length vector ("unit vector") η pointing towards an object in the sky ("on the celestial sphere") in terms of RA (ϕ) and Dec (θ) angles is given by

$$\eta = \cos(\theta) \cos(\phi) \mathbf{x} + \cos(\theta) \sin(\phi) \mathbf{y} + \sin(\theta) \mathbf{z} = C (c \mathbf{x} + s \mathbf{y}) + S \mathbf{z}$$

The arc angle Θ_{12} between any two directions in the sky η_1 and η_2 (or any two stars) using the dot product formula and some obvious abbreviations, satisfies

$$\cos(\Theta_{12}) = \sin(\theta_1)\sin(\theta_2) + \cos(\theta_1)\cos(\theta_2)\cos(\phi_1-\phi_2) = S_1S_2 + C_1C_2c_{1-2}$$

$$1 \text{ degree} = \pi/180 \text{ radians} = 1.745 \cdot 10^{-2} \text{ radians}$$

$$1 \text{ arcmin} = \pi/10800 \text{ radians} = 2.909 \cdot 10^{-4} \text{ radians}$$

$$1 \text{ arcsec} = 1 \text{ asec} = \pi/648000 \text{ radians} = 4.848 \cdot 10^{-6} \text{ radians}$$

$$1 \text{ mas} = 10^{-3} \text{ asec} = 4.848 \cdot 10^{-9} \text{ radians}$$

$$1 \text{ asec @ 1 km} = 4.848 \text{ mm}$$

$$1 \text{ asec @ 1 AU} = 725.3 \text{ km}$$

$$1 \text{ asec @ 1 pc} = 1.0000 \text{ AU}$$

$$1 \text{ mas @ 1 kpc} = 1.0000 \text{ AU}$$

JD = Julian Date (Astronomer's calendar) = a simple count of days starting at noon UT on Monday 1 Jan 4713 BC. That date and time was the start of Julian Day 0. The current JD can be inferred from the value on the cover of the Trapezium.

The Brightest Stars

The 80 brightest stars (c/o Wikipedia), and their distances from Earth in light years.

1	Sirius	8.6	41	Menkalinan	81.1
2	Canopus	309.2	42	Atria	390.6
3	alpha Centauri	4.4	43	Alhena	109.3
4	Arcturus	36.7	44	Peacock	178.8
5	Vega	25.0	45	Alsephina	80.6
6	Capella	42.8	46	Mirzam	492.7
7	Rigel	862.8	47	Polaris	432.6
8	Procyon	11.5	48	Alphard	177.3
9	Archenar	139.4	49	Hamal	65.8
10	Betelgeuse	497.9	50	Diphda	96.3
11	beta Centauri	392.0	51	Mizar	97.8
12	Altair	16.7	52	Nunki	227.8
13	alpha Crucis	322.0	53	Menkent	58.8
14	Aldebaran	66.6	54	Alpheratz	97.0
15	Antares	553.7	55	Mirach	197.4
16	Spica	249.7	56	Rasalhague	48.6
17	Pollux	33.8	57	Algieba	130.1
18	Fomalhaut	25.1	58	Kochab	130.9
19	Deneb	1411.9	59	Saiph	647.1
20	Mimosa	278.5	60	Denebola	35.9
21	Regulus	79.3	61	Algol	94.0
22	Adhara	405.2	62	Tiaki	177.0
23	Castor	50.9	63	Muhlifain	130.2
24	Shaula	571.2	64	Aspidiske	765.6
25	Gacrux	88.6	65	Suhail	544.5
26	Bellatrix	252.4	66	Alphecca	75.0
27	Elnath	133.9	67	Mintaka	692.5
28	Miaplacidus	113.2	68	Sadr	1832.3
29	Alnilam	1976.7	69	Eltanin	154.3
30	Regor	1117.0	70	Schedar	228.2
31	Alnair	101.0	71	Naos	1083.6
32	Alnitak	736.2	72	Almach	393.0
33	Alioth	82.6	73	Caph	54.7
34	Dubhe	122.9	74	Izar	235.8
35	Mirfak	506.5	75	alpha Lupi	464.6
36	Wezen	1606.7	76	epsilon Centauri	427.5
37	Sargas	329.5	77	Dschubba	491.2
38	Kaus Australis	143.3	78	Larawag	63.7
39	Avior	605.1	79	eta Centauri	305.7
40	Alkaid	103.9	80	Merak	79.7

Notable Star-Pair Angles

Notable star pairs (of the set of the 80 brightest stars listed above) that are close to a multiple of 5° separation:

		Θ	$\Delta\theta$ [deg.]
Schedar	Caph	5	-0.085
Betelgeuse	Alnitak	10	0.017
Capella	Castor	30	-0.023
Procyon	Mirzam	30	-0.094
Elnath	Alnilam	30	-0.096
Alpheratz	Caph	30	0.060
Aldebaran	Pollux	45	0.013
Betelgeuse	Algol	50	-0.033
Alnitak	Naos	50	-0.049
Pollux	Alioth	60	0.065
Gacrux	Alphard	60	-0.001
Regulus	Bellatrix	70	-0.030
Sirius	Mirfak	80	-0.094
alpha_Centauri	Regulus	90	0.057
Vega	Denebola	90	-0.065
Fomalhaut	Caph	90	0.006
Deneb	Alnilam	120	0.059
Menkent	Mintaka	120	0.000
Sirius	Alphecca	135	-0.089
Aldebaran	Antares	170	-0.021

Exeunt

“And somewhere as in blind night, on a mild sea, a sailor may be made aware of an iceberg, fanged and mortal, bearing invisibly near, by the unwarmed charm of its breath, nothingness now revealed itself:

“that permanent night upon which the stars in their expiring generations are less than the glinting of gnats, and nebulae, more trivial than winter breath; that darkness in which eternity lies bent and pale, a dead snake in a jar, and infinity is the sparkling of a wren blown out to sea; that inconceivable chasm of invulnerable silence in which the cataclysms of galaxies rave mute as amber.”

- James Rufus Agee (1909-1955)
fm. A Death in the Family
(publ. 1957)

ORION and TAO (and Obed) General Information (links)

May be found at the following URLs:

https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Tamke-Allan_Observatory

<http://www.orioninc.org/>

<https://orionastronomy.wordpress.com>

<https://www.facebook.com/ORIONAstronomyTN/>

<https://www.facebook.com/groups/454645124557215>

<https://www.facebook.com/pages/Tamke-Allan%20Observatory/120477734665841>

<https://www.roanestate.edu/?349-Tamke-Allan-Observatory>

<https://www.roanestate.edu/pages/obs/index.htm>

<https://twitter.com/TAOremote>

ORIONastronomy@groups.io

Where is TAO?

334 Caney Creek Rd, Rockwood, TN 37854

N 35° 49' 57", W 84° 37' 04"; Alt. 324 m

Where is Obed?

Lilly Bluff Overlook

N 36° 06' 09", W 84° 43' 17"; Alt. 402 m

Nemo Bridge (on the bridge, E bank of Emory River)

N 36° 04' 07", W 84° 39' 43"; Alt. 268 m

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Vol. 50, Issue 03; Fri 15 Mar 2024:	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10822600
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Fin du journal

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